

REVERSIBLE CARDIOMYOPATHY WITH PERICARDIAL EFFUSION IN A MYXEDEMA PATIENT*Ismibayli Z.,
MD**Nazirova V.
MD**Cardiology Department, XMSK Hospital, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

We report a case of secondary cardiomyopathy with pericardial effusion due to long-standing untreated hypothyroidism with a successful resolution of clinical symptoms and improvement of echocardiographic parameters in a relatively short period of time.

Keywords: Cardiomyopathy, myxedema, heart failure, pericardial effusion.

Introduction

Cardiomyopathy is the second leading cardiovascular cause of death after coronary artery disease. Despite the major advances in defining the etiopathogenic mechanisms of different types of cardiomyopathies, and evolvement of medical treatment options, prognosis of such patients remains poor. Hypothyroidism-induced cardiomyopathy on the other hand is an example where good results can be achieved. We present a case of such example, with great improvement of clinical and hemodynamic parameters in a patient with secondary cardiomyopathy.

Case Report

A 50-year-old woman presented to our hospital with progressive weakness and dyspnea rated as New York Heart Association Functional Class III. She reported at least 5-year history of general weakness, hair loss, dry skin and cold intolerance. Several months ago she had a pleural puncture due to bilateral pleural effusion with no further work up.

On physical examination the patient was awake and oriented, but strikingly apathetic with slow mentation. Vital signs showed a temperature of 32.5°C, blood pressure 119/90 mm Hg, heart rate 103 beats per minute, respiratory rate 18 breaths per minute and oxygen saturation 93% on room air. She had cool, dry skin, mild bilateral lower extremity non-pitting edema. The thyroid was not palpable. Cardiovascular examination showed distant heart sounds, no crackles were heard on lung auscultation.

The cardiac silhouette was enlarged on CXR and the lung fields were clear. ECG revealed a sinus rhythm with non-specific repolarization changes (Figure 1).

Transthoracic echocardiography (Figure 2a,b,c) showed a dilated left ventricle with a diastolic dimension of 58 mm and severely depressed systolic ejection fraction (LVEF) of 15–20%, severe diffuse hypokinesis, a moderate degree of mitral regurgitation, mild-to-moderate circumferential pericardial effusion with signs of pre-tamponade physiology (right atrial collapse and plethoric inferior vena cava, with no diastolic RV collapse or exaggerated respiratory mitral and tricuspid valve in-flow velocity changes).

Blood tests revealed normal platelets and white blood cell count, low hemoglobin (116 g/l), normal MCV (81.4 fL), RBC ($4.41 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), ferritin (84.61 ng/ml), glucose (4.73 mmol/l) and creatinine (72.1 $\mu\text{mol/l}$). The level of TSH was grossly elevated ($>100 \mu\text{IU/ml}$).

Given the fact that there were no clinical features of cardiac tamponade and no risk factors suggesting ischemic etiology of heart failure, medical treatment consisting of 50 mcg/day of Levothyroxine and starting doses of Ramipril and Carvedilol was initiated and gradually increased during close follow-up visits.

Three months after the initial presentation patient had excellent clinical improvement with complete resolution of symptoms. On transthoracic echocardiography (3a,b) there were no signs of pericardial effusion, LVEF went up to 50%, with LVDD diameter of 48 mm. TSH was normal (2.3 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$). Medical treatment continued with Levothyroxine 75mcg/day, Carvedilol 6.25 mg BID, and Ramipril 2.5 mg BID. Further up-titration of ACE inhibitors and β -blockers was difficult due to persistent hypotension. The patient continued to be followed-up and altogether showed a good outcome.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Discussion

Cardiomyopathy is a myocardial disorder in which the heart muscle is structurally and functionally abnormal, in the absence of coronary artery disease, hypertension, valvular disease and congenital heart disease sufficient to cause the observed myocardial abnormality. (1)

According to the latest classification proposed by American Heart Association in 2006, the term primary should be used to describe diseases in which the heart is the sole or predominantly involved organ and secondary to describe diseases in which myocardial dysfunction is part of a systemic disorder. (2) Primary cardiomyopathies are divided into genetic, mixed (genetic and nongenetic), and acquired forms. Secondary cardiomyopathies, previously referred to as specific cardiomyopathies, are diseases with myocardial involvement as part of a large variety of multiorgan disorders. Hypothyroidism-induced cardiomyopathy therefore is one of the examples of secondary cardiomyopathy.

It is well known that thyroid hormone has a great effect on the heart and vascular system. (3) Minor alteration of thyroid hormone can change vascular resistance, cardiac contractility, blood pressure, and heart rhythm.

The concept that the heart could be affected in hypothyroidism is at least a hundred years old. First time the 'myxedema heart' term was proposed by Zondek in 1918, and the concept has ever since been investigated by a vast number of clinical studies. (4), (5), (6)

The prognosis of primary, and especially genetic cardiomyopathies is usually quite poor due to a progressive and irreversible myocardial dysfunction, whereas hypothyroidism-induced cardiomyopathy carries a better prognosis and can be reversed with hormone supplementation. It is therefore recommended to investigate an underlying hypothyroidism in all patients newly presenting with Heart Failure (HF). (7)

In our patient, repletion of thyroid hormone deficiency led to complete resolution of clinical signs and symptoms of HF along with dramatic improvement of echocardiographic parameters in quite a short period of time despite the presumably long-standing hypothyroid state and the use of suboptimal doses of HF medications. This case confirms previous reports of reversibility of heart failure after substitutive hormonal treatment. (8), (9)

Written consent

Obtained from patient

Disclosures

Nil

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